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Vermont 2024-2025 Colony Loss Report

Samantha A. Alger*, M. Sydney Miller*, P. Alexander Burnham*[†], Andrew Munkres[§]

*University of Vermont, Agriculture, Landscape, and Environment Department

[†]University of Vermont, Department of Biology

[§]Vermont Beekeepers Association

University
of Vermont

Colony loss surveys are a critical tool for understanding honey bee health, management challenges, and the overall productivity of the beekeeping industry. Reliable data on colony losses provide essential insight into the pressures faced by beekeepers and inform efforts to improve honey bee health at both state and national levels.

The Vermont Bee Lab at the University of Vermont conducted surveys by phone to capture 2024-2025 colony loss data from Vermont beekeeping operations (see survey questions below, Box 1 & Box 2). This survey focused primarily on commercial (managing 300+ colonies) and sideline operations (managing 20-299 colonies), to capture data from Vermont's larger, professionally managed apiaries that best reflect the state's beekeeping industry. Both migratory (moving colonies seasonally across state or regional lines) and stationary operations (keeping colonies in fixed locations year-round) were included. Survey data captured responses from 12 beekeeping operations representing a total of 6,434 colonies, approximately 35.7% of the 18,013 colonies that were registered by Vermont beekeepers with the state in 2024¹.

Vermont beekeepers reported an **overall total annual colony loss of 56.08%** across all surveyed operations in 2024-2025. When separated by operation type, migratory beekeepers experienced an annual loss of **56.36%**, while stationary operations reported a slightly higher **58.31%**. **Winter losses** were significant for both groups, averaging **47.96%** overall. Migratory operations reported a total winter loss of **42.48%**, whereas stationary beekeepers experienced higher losses at **58.22%**. In contrast, **summer losses** were much lower, averaging **15.61%**, but still varied between groups: migratory operations lost **24.14%** of colonies, while stationary beekeepers reported minimal summer loss (**0.22%**). According to respondents, the top causes of loss were pesticide exposure and *Varroa* followed by nutrition and diseases.

BEEKEEPING OPERATION TYPE	COLONY COUNT			TOTAL COLONY LOSS		
	Spring 2024	Fall 2025	Spring 2025	Winter 2024-2025	Summer 2025	Annual 2024-2025
MIGRATORY	3,273	3,721	2,910	42.48%	24.14%	56.36%
STATIONARY	1,650	2,713	1,128	58.22%	0.22%	58.31%
TOTALS:	4,923	6,434	4,038	47.96%	15.61%	56.08%

Table 1: 2024 - 2025 colony count loss for Vermont. Colony counts represent the number of colonies reported in our survey in Spring of 2024, Fall of 2025 and the Spring of 2025. Colony loss represents total colony lost^{2,3} during the winter, summer and the entire 2024-2025 beekeeping season. All values are broken out by migratory and stationary operations and total values were also computed.

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Figure 1: Percent total loss for Vermont. Colony loss described over three periods: Summer 2025, Winter 2024-2025, and the entire year Spring 2024-Spring 2025. Migratory and stationary operations are shown in blue and orange, respectively.

Methods

The survey methodology used in this report follows the widely accepted framework outlined by the Bee Informed Partnership (BIP) surveys and others²⁻⁷. The framework provides a standardized approach for assessing honey bee colony losses across time and management systems^{2,3} and accounts for changes in colony numbers throughout the year—including purchases, sales, and splits—to provide a more accurate measure of true mortality. By distinguishing between winter and summer losses and between migratory and stationary colonies, it offers seasonally and regionally relevant insights that align with national standards while reflecting the realities of Vermont beekeeping.

In brief, colony loss rates were determined by dividing the total number of colonies lost by the total number of colonies at risk during a specified time period. Colonies at risk included those alive at the beginning of the period, along with any new colonies created or acquired, while excluding colonies that were sold or otherwise removed from the operation. The annual loss period extended from April 1 to the following April 1, with summer loss representing the interval from the date of the first reported split through October 1, and winter loss covering the period from that point until the next April 1.

Conclusion

Vermont beekeepers reported substantial colony losses during the 2024–2025 season, underscoring ongoing challenges for the industry. To place these results in a broader context, surveys led by Auburn University and the Apiary Inspectors of America (AIA), with support from Oregon State University estimated total U.S. colony losses for the same 2024-2025 period at 55.6%, the highest annual loss recorded since tracking began in 2010–2011, and 14.8 percentage points higher than the running 13-year average annual loss rate of 40.3%⁸. These estimates indicate that U.S. beekeeping operations lost more colonies during the 2024-2025 season than in any other year on record⁸. State-specific data from this national survey are also available for Vermont, capturing responses from 48 beekeepers managing 1,054 colonies, with a total annual loss of 61.76% and ranking 9th highest losses of the 41 states that provided data. These figures likely represent more hobbyist-level operations than commercial or sideline operations, as indicated by the relatively high number of respondents but smaller total colony numbers compared with the UVM survey. In response to abnormal colony losses reported nationwide in January 2025 by US commercial beekeepers, Project Apis M and the American Beekeeping Federation conducted two surveys across the US accounting for over 50% of all U.S. colonies and reported total net colony losses of 55.3% and 40.2%, respectively⁹. Together, these national and state-level data provide context for understanding how Vermont’s beekeepers fit within broader trends in colony loss across the United States. They show that Vermont is consistent with the high colony losses reported nationwide during the 2024-2025 season—Vermont’s beekeepers are not an exception to this widespread pattern.

Acknowledgements

Thank you to the Vermont beekeepers who participated in this survey. We appreciate the time you took to share colony numbers and management details with us. These data are not “just numbers”—they represent real management choices, risks, investments, and the everyday realities of keeping bees alive in a challenging landscape. Thank you for your trust, your transparency, and your commitment to improving bee health in Vermont.

References

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Box 1. The survey questions for stationary beekeepers

Are you a migratory beekeeper, (i.e., your bees spend the winter outside of VT)?
Possible answers presented were Migratory or Stationary. If the beekeeper answered Stationary, the surveyor remained in Box 1 questions. If the beekeeper answered Migratory, the surveyor moved to Box 2 questions.
Which Vermont counties are your apiaries located in?
Multiple choice question, multiple selection allowed. Possible answers presented were all Vermont counties.
When did you start making splits in 2024?
Date entry.
When did you start making splits in 2025?
Date entry.
How many colonies did you own at each date? April 1, 2024
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How many colonies did you own at each date? October 1, 2024
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How many colonies did you own at each date? April 1, 2025
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How many colonies did you obtain from outside your operation during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (April 1 2024-Oct 1 2024)
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How many colonies did you obtain from outside your operation during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (Oct 1 2024-April 1 2025)
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How much net increase in colonies did you make from splitting your own colonies during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (April 1 2024-Oct 1 2024)
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How much net increase in colonies did you make from splitting your own colonies during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (Oct 1 2024-April 1 2025)
Numeric entry (positive integers).
How many colonies did you sell or give away during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (April 1 2024-Oct 1 2024)
Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you sell or give away during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (Oct 1 2024-April 1 2025)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How much was your net decrease in colonies due to intentionally combining your colonies during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (April 1 2024-Oct 1 2024)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How much was your net decrease in colonies due to intentionally combining your colonies during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (Oct 1 2024-April 1 2025)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

What do you believe to be the major reasons for colony loss during the Winter 2024-2025?

Possible answers presented were Nutrition, Disease, Varroa mites, Pesticide exposure, Uncertain, All of the above

Box 2. The survey questions for migratory beekeepers

Are you a migratory beekeeper, (i.e., your bees spend the winter outside of VT)?

Possible answers presented were Migratory or Stationary. If beekeeper answered Migratory, surveyor remained in Box 2 questions. If beekeeper answered Stationary, surveyor moved to Box 1 questions.

What date did you begin moving colonies out of Vermont in 2024?

Date entry.

What date did you begin moving colonies back into Vermont in 2025?

Date entry.

How many colonies are you bringing back north in spring 2025?

Numeric entry (positive integers).

Which Vermont counties are your apiaries located in?

Multiple choice question, multiple selection allowed. Possible answers presented were all Vermont counties.

Which states did your colonies travel to during the 2024-2025 winter?

Multiple choice question, multiple selection allowed. Possible answers presented all US States, the District of Columbia, Puerto Rico and an "other" category to specify in open entry.

On what date did you start splitting in 2024?

Date entry. Used as Summer start date in subsequent questions.

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On what date did you start splitting in 2025?

Date entry. Used as Winter end date in subsequent questions.

How many colonies did you own at each date? When first split was made in 2024

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you own at each date? October 1, 2024

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you own at each date? When first split was made in 2025

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you obtain from outside your operation during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (Start date of splitting in 2024 – October 1, 2024)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you obtain from outside your operation during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025. (October 1, 2024 – Start date of splitting in 2025)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How much net increase in colonies did you make from splitting your own colonies during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (Start date of splitting in 2024 – October 1, 2024)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How much net increase in colonies did you make from splitting your own colonies during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (October 1, 2024 – Start date of splitting in 2025)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you sell or give away during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (Start date of splitting in 2024 – October 1, 2024)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How many colonies did you sell or give away during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (October 1, 2024 – Start date of splitting in 2025)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How much was your net decrease in colonies due to intentionally combining your colonies during each seasonal period? Summer 2024 (Start date of splitting in 2024 – October 1, 2024)

Numeric entry (positive integers).

How much was your net decrease in colonies due to intentionally combining your colonies during each seasonal period? Winter 2024-2025 (October 1, 2024 – Start date of splitting in 2025)

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Numeric entry (positive integers).

What do you believe to be the major reasons for colony loss during the Winter 2024-2025?

Possible answers presented were Nutrition, Disease, Varroa mites, Pesticide exposure, Uncertain, All of the above